

Digital Simulation of Electromagnetic Wave Diffraction by a Rectangular Groove in a Conducting Screen

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Abstract. When optimizing the directivity and energy characteristics of the antennas with flat reflectors and the leaky-wave antennas, high-speed computational algorithms are required for a reliable analysis of the diffraction of electromagnetic waves on a conducting screen, accounting for the inhomogeneities with the dimensions commensurate with the wavelength. To calculate the diffraction field of an electromagnetic wave with an arbitrary-shaped front on a rectangular groove in the screen, a numerical model has been developed. This model is based on the approximation of the wave front by finite locally flat patches and the use of the authors' rigorous solution of the problem of locally flat wave diffraction on a conducting screen with a groove. The field above the screen is represented by the Fourier integral, while the field in the groove – by the sum of waveguide modes. The set of functional equations is obtained using the method of partial domains. Through a re-expansion of the modal functions of the field of partial domains in terms of the basis of the adjacent domain, the functional equations are reduced to a set of linear algebraic equations with respect to the complex amplitudes of the waveguide modes of the groove. The implementation of the main computational procedures is described. Based on the analysis of the particular results, the reliability of the developed model is proved. The influence of the quality of the wave front interpolation on the accuracy of the solution is studied. Recommendations on the frequency of a wave-front fragmentation are formulated. The proposed digital algorithm can be used to analyze and synthesize antennas with the flat perforated distributing and radiating systems.

INTRODUCTION

The problem of electromagnetic wave diffraction on a local inhomogeneity is one of the key problems arising in the analysis and synthesis of a number of super high frequency (SHF) and extremely high frequency (EHF) devices, as well as the distributing and radiating systems of the certain classes of antennas [1]-[6]. Among the wide variety of the types of inhomogeneities, a special place is occupied by a groove in the screen – a through one or shorted. The set of grooves in the screen forms a diffracting comb-type array widely used as a functional element of transmission lines and radiating antenna apertures with both parallel (optical) [7]-[11] and sequential [12]-[17] excitation modes. Thus, the problem of an electromagnetic wave diffraction on a groove in a conducting screen is of particular interest and is in urgent need of an effective solution. The efficiency of the introduced solution is understood to be in its universality in terms of the type of an exposure and it also presupposes the algorithm computational efficiency, simultaneously allowing taking into account the entire spectrum of the possible resonant phenomena in the groove.

In many practical applications, the source of the electromagnetic field is located in the immediate vicinity of the groove. The consequence of this is a nontrivial shape of the amplitude-phase front of the wave interacting with the groove in the screen. Obviously, the approximation of the field incident on the groove by a flat electromagnetic wave is not only insufficient in this case, it is also incorrect, since the reliability of the solution requires taking into account the structure of the incident field.

The traditional computational algorithms for analyzing the diffraction of a wave with a nonplane front on a groove in a conducting screen are based on the representation of the scattered (secondary) field as a continuous spatial Fourier spectrum of flat waves. When describing the primary field by a wave beam, the Fourier expansion of the beam into flat waves unbounded in space is also used. As a result, the analysis of the diffraction of the field of a lumped source is reduced to a multiple solution of the problem of a flat wave scattering on a groove in the screen [18]-[21]. This method of formalizing the problem is the most effective one in the case of a relatively compact spatial spectrum of the primary wave beam. In SHF and EHF antenna applications, this condition is met relatively rarely.

The alternative method is based on the representation of the front of the primary wave as locally flat in the aggregate of points on the surface of the screen with a groove [22], [23]. Then the primary field can be replaced by a finite sum of artificially local flat waves (with the flat fronts artificially bounded in their extension in space) [24]. With this approach, the scattering characteristics are calculated using the superposition principle based on a solution to the problem of a diffraction of a locally flat wave on a rectangular groove in the screen.

The purpose of the work is to mathematically formalize the problem of a diffraction of a wave with a complex amplitude-phase front on a rectangular groove in a conducting screen and to numerically test the influence of the accuracy of a wave front interpolation by locally flat waves on the solution error.

THE DIFFRACTION PROBLEM MATHEMATICAL MODEL GENERATION

The diffraction problem is considered in 2D space (Fig. 1). Regular in the direction of the Oy axis, a rectangular groove with a width of $2a$ and a depth of h is made in a screen that is unbounded in the xOy plane and has an ideal conductivity.

FIGURE 1. The geometry of the diffraction problem and a description of the field by the aggregate of the locally flat waves with the nonoverlapping fronts.

The groove in the screen is excited by a linear H -polarization electromagnetic wave diverging from the point with the coordinates (x_0, z_0) with a known and, in a general case, arbitrary amplitude-phase distribution on the groove mouth, described by the intensity function $Q(x)$.

A segment of the Ox axis of the length $2\Delta = x_K - x_1$ is symmetrical to the center of the groove and divided into equal parts by the points with the coordinates x_i , where $i = \overline{1, K}$, K is the number of the wave front sampling points. In the neighbourhood of each of the x_i points, the amplitude-phase front of an electromagnetic wave incident on the screen with a groove will be considered locally flat. Then the field of such a wave along the Ox axis can be described by a finite sum of the linear H -polarization waves with the flat fronts artificially bounded in their extension and nonoverlapping in space:

$$H_y^{(p)}(x) = \sum_{i=1}^K Q(x_i) \exp[j\beta_i(x-x_i)] [1(x-x_{1i}) - 1(x-x_{2i})], \quad (1)$$

where β_i is the constant of propagation of the i -th locally flat wave with the amplitude $Q(x_i)$, not equal to 0 within the interval $[x_{1i}, x_{2i}]$, in the direction of the axis Ox :

$$\beta_i = k \sin \varphi_i = k(x_i - x_0) / \sqrt{(x_i - x_0)^2 + z_0^2}; \quad x_{1i} = x_i - \Delta l_i, \quad x_{2i} = x_i + \Delta l_i;$$

$2\Delta l_i$ is the length of the surface fragment exposed by the i -th wave; $k = 2\pi/\lambda$, λ is the wavelength in a free space; φ_i is the direction of the i -th wave arrival from the point (x_0, z_0) into the point $(x_i, 0)$; $1(x)$ is the Heaviside function: $1(x) = 1$, if $x \geq 0$, and $1(x) = 0$, if $x < 0$.

To reach the goal, one must solve the problem of diffraction of the i -th locally flat wave of the linear H -polarization on the groove in the conducting screen (Fig. 2).

FIGURE 2. The geometry of the diffraction of the locally flat wave on the groove in the screen with the wave front bounded in its extension.

The electromagnetic field of such wave is described by the non-zero H -component oriented in the direction of its homogeneity that, according to (1), is:

$$H_y^{(0)}(x, z) = Q(x_i) [1(x-x_{1i}(z)) - 1(x-x_{2i}(z))] \exp[j\beta_i(x-x_i)] \exp(-j\gamma_i z),$$

where $x_{1i}(z)$ are the abscissas of the left and right boundaries of the band exposed by the locally flat wave: $x_{1i}(z) = x_i + z \tan \varphi_i \mp \Delta l_i$, $\Delta l_i = x_2 - x_1$; x_i is the abscissa of the center of the band exposed by the wave; $\gamma_i = k \cos \varphi_i$ is the crossing (in the Oz direction) propagation constant.

It is advisable to represent the field scattered by the groove in the space above the groove as an integral Fourier expansion into the classical flat waves with the unbounded fronts [25]:

$$H_y^{(d)}(x, z) = \int_{-\infty}^{\infty} A(\beta) \exp[j(\beta x + \gamma(\beta) z)] d\beta,$$

where β and $\gamma(\beta) = \sqrt{k^2 - \beta^2}$ are the partial flat wave propagation constants included in the spatial scattering spectrum; $A(\beta)$ is the complex spectral density of the field intensity.

The diffraction field inside the groove that has a form of the shorted flat waveguide should be approximated by the discrete aggregate of the waveguide modes [25]:

$$H_y^{(i)}(x, z) = \sum_{m=0}^{\infty} D_{mi} \cos[\eta_m(z+h)] f_m(x),$$

where D_{mi} is the complex amplitude of the m -th mode with the Oz -axis oriented propagation constant equal to $\eta_m = \sqrt{k^2 - (m\pi/2a)^2}$;

$$f_m(x) = \begin{cases} \cos[m\pi(x+a)/2a], & |x| \leq a, \\ 0, & |x| > a \end{cases}$$

is the modal function ensuring fulfilling the boundary conditions on the conducting walls of the groove.

The components of the electric field above and inside the groove are determined by the H_y -component according to the Maxwell equations [25]. As a result of conjugation, the tangential field component, at $z = 0$, allows producing the following set of the functional equations:

$$\int_{-\infty}^{\infty} [A(\beta) - \delta(\beta - \beta_i) Q(x_i) \exp(-j\beta x_i) (1(x - x_{li}) - 1(x - x_{ri}))] \gamma(\beta) \exp(j\beta x) d\beta =$$

$$= j \sum_{m=0}^{\infty} D_{mi} \eta_m \sin(\eta_m h) f_m(x), \quad -\infty < x < \infty, \quad (2)$$

$$\int_{-\infty}^{\infty} [A(\beta) + \delta(\beta - \beta_i) Q(x_i) \exp(-j\beta x_i) (1(x - x_{li}) - 1(x - x_{ri}))] \gamma(\beta) \exp(j\beta x) d\beta =$$

$$= j \sum_{m=0}^{\infty} D_{mi} \cos(\eta_m h) f_m(x), \quad |x| \leq a, \quad (3)$$

where $\delta(\beta - \beta_i)$ is the Dirac delta function allowing introducing the components of the primary locally flat wave field into the complex spectral density of the field intensity above the groove.

If both parts of the equation (2) are multiplied by $\exp(-j\beta x)$ and the resulting expression are integrated by the variable x in infinite limits [26], then the expression for the spectral density $A(\beta)$ can be obtained, which, after replacing β' by β , takes the form

$$A(\beta) = \frac{1}{2\pi\gamma(\beta)} \left[Q(x_i) \gamma_i K_i(\beta) + j \sum_{m=0}^{\infty} D_{mi} \eta_m \sin(\eta_m h) I_m(\beta) \right]. \quad (4)$$

In (4),

$$I_m(\beta) = \int_{-\infty}^{\infty} f_m(x) \exp(-j\beta x) dx = a \exp(-jm\pi/2) \left[\text{sinc}(\beta a + m\pi/2) + (-1)^m \text{sinc}(\beta a - m\pi/2) \right],$$

$$K_i(\beta) = \exp(-j\beta_i x_i) \int_{x_{li}}^{x_{ri}} \exp[-jx(\beta - \beta_i)] dx = 2\Delta l_i \exp(-j\beta x_i) \text{sinc}[\Delta l_i(\beta - \beta_i)],$$

and $\text{sinc}(u) = \sin(u)/u$.

The expansion of the function $\exp(-j\beta x)$ into an orthogonal (within the interval $|x| \leq a$) system of functions [26] makes it possible to exclude the spatial coordinate x from the functional equation (3):

$$\int_{-\infty}^{\infty} A(\beta) I_s^*(\beta) d\beta + (-D_{si}) \cos(\eta_s h) (1 + \Delta_s^0) a = -Q(x_i) J_{si}, \quad s = \overline{0, \infty}, \quad (5)$$

where Δ_s^t is the Kronecker symbol; $I_s^*(\beta)$ is the complex conjugation to $I_m(\beta)$ accounting for the change of m by s ;

$$J_{si} = \int_{-\infty}^{\infty} [1(x - x_{li}) - 1(x - x_{ri})] \exp[j\beta_i(x - x_i)] [1(x + a) - 1(x - a)] \cos[s\pi(x + a)/2a] dx$$

are the coefficients of the excitation resulting from the direct effect of the locally flat wave on the groove.

It is noteworthy that if $x_{li} \leq -a$ or, i.e. when the groove is not directly exposed by the local flat wave, the coefficients J_{si} are identically equal to 0, while, for the other values of x_{li} , x_{ri} , these coefficients can be found analytically, in accordance with the expression:

$$J_{si} = \int_{\rho_{li}}^{\rho_{ri}} \exp[j\beta_i(x - x_i)] \cos[s\pi(x + a)/2a] dx.$$

$$\text{where } \rho_{li} = \begin{cases} -a, & x_{li} \leq -a, \\ x_{li}, & -a < x_{li} < a, \end{cases} \quad \rho_{ri} = \begin{cases} a, & x_{ri} \geq a, \\ x_{ri}, & -a < x_{ri} < a. \end{cases}$$

The elimination of the complex spectral density $A(\beta)$, defined by the expression (4), from (5) makes it possible to obtain a set of linear algebraic equations (SLAE) describing the complex amplitudes of the waveguide modes of the groove:

$$\sum_{m=0}^{\infty} D_{mi} \left[\eta_m \sin(\eta_m h) \sigma_{ms} + j \Delta_m^s (1 + \Delta_s^0) a \cos(\eta_m h) \right] = j Q(x_i) (J_{si} + \gamma_i P_{si}).$$

where

$$\sigma_{ms} = \frac{1}{2\pi} \int_{-\infty}^{\infty} \frac{1}{\gamma(\beta)} I_m(\beta) I_s^*(\beta) d\beta = \frac{1}{2\pi} \int_{-\infty}^{\infty} \frac{1}{\sqrt{k^2 - \beta^2}} \int_0^{2a} \cos\left(\frac{m\pi}{2a} x\right) \exp(-j\beta x) dx \int_0^{2a} \cos\left(\frac{s\pi}{2a} x\right) \exp(j\beta x) dx d\beta \quad (6)$$

are the coefficients of the electrodynamic ties of the modes in the field above the groove;

$$P_{si} = \frac{1}{2\pi} \int_{-\infty}^{\infty} \frac{1}{\gamma(\beta)} K_i(\beta) I_s^*(\beta) d\beta = \frac{1}{2\pi} \int_{-\infty}^{\infty} \frac{\exp[-j(\beta a + \beta_i x_i)]}{\sqrt{k^2 - \beta^2}} \int_{x_i}^{x_{ri}} \exp[-jx(\beta - \beta_i)] dx \int_0^{2a} \cos\left(\frac{s\pi}{2a} x\right) \exp(j\beta x) dx d\beta \quad (7)$$

are the coefficients of the excitation that occurs due to the electrodynamic link between the groove modes and an excited surface band exposed by a locally flat wave.

The problem of diffraction of an aggregate of locally flat waves (1) on a groove in a screen belongs to the class of the linear problems for which the superposition principle is valid. Therefore, the SLAE, which determines the waveguide modes of a groove during the diffraction of a single locally flat wave, can be directly used to calculate the electrodynamic response of a screen with a groove to the sum of locally flat waves. This would require only a simple modification of the right side of the SLAE, determined by the conditions for the excitation of the groove in the screen, – namely, some additional terms should be introduced as follows:

$$\sum_{m=0}^{\infty} D_m \left[\eta_m \sin(\eta_m h) \sigma_{ms} + j \Delta_m^s (1 + \Delta_s^0) a \cos(\eta_m h) \right] = j \sum_{i=1}^K Q(x_i) \exp(-j\beta_i x_i) (J_{si} + \gamma_i P_{si}), \quad (8)$$

where D_m is the complex amplitude of the m -th waveguide mode of the groove.

The complex amplitudes of the waveguide modes D_m of the groove obtained while solving the truncated SLAE (8) are used to calculate the complex spectral density of the field scattered by the screen with the groove:

$$A(\beta) = \frac{1}{2\pi\sqrt{k^2 - \beta^2}} \left[\sum_{i=1}^K Q(x_i) \gamma_i K_i(\beta) + j \sum_{m=0}^{\infty} D_m \eta_m \sin(\eta_m h) I_m(\beta) \right]. \quad (9)$$

The first term in (9) describes the contribution of the radiation from the excited part of the screen, which complements the groove aperture, while the second term stands for the own response of the groove. When studying the direct contribution of the groove to the formation of the scattered field, the first term should be omitted.

To estimate the nonnormalized amplitude diagram of the wave scattering induced by the groove – that is the amplitude of the diffraction field in the far zone as a function of the observation angle – one should use the formula obtained in [27]:

$$f(\Theta) = 2\pi\sqrt{30k} |A(k \sin \Theta)| \cos \Theta. \quad (10)$$

where Θ is the observation angle measured clockwise from the normal to the screen.

IMPLEMENTATION OF THE BASIC COMPUTATIONAL PROCEDURES AND THE MODEL RELIABILITY ESTIMATION

The truncation of SLAE (8) is performed by simply limiting the number of waveguide modes taken into account in the groove ($m, s = 0, \overline{M}$). Numerical analysis shows that to ensure a power balance error of 0.5% or less, it is sufficient to take into account all the modes propagating in the groove and two or three of the decaying ones. The resulting SLAE dimension is not large and includes no more than 3-5 equations in the resonant mode ($\lambda \sim 2\Delta$).

This value is at least one or two orders less than the number of equations produced by means of the methods based on space or time discretization.

The main time costs when developing SLAE (8) fall on the calculation of the coefficients. The equation (6) for the coefficients σ_{ms} is suitable for a numerical calculation. At the same time, it was shown in [26] that the expression similar to (6) can be reduced to a form more adapted to numerical calculations. If one considers (6) as the Fourier transform (a spectrum) of the product of the two functions, then, assuming that the spectrum of the product of the functions is equal to the integral convolution of the spectra of these functions, one can obtain:

$$\sigma_{ms} = \frac{1}{2} \int_{-2a}^{2a} H_0^{(1)}(k|\xi|) \int_{\mu_l}^{\mu_1} \cos\left[\frac{m\pi(\mu + \xi)}{2a}\right] \cos\left(\frac{s\pi\mu}{2a}\right) d\mu d\xi, \quad (11)$$

where $H_0^{(1)}(x)$ is the zero-order Hankel function of the first kind; $\mu_l = \begin{cases} -\xi, & \xi \leq 0, \\ 0, & \xi > 0; \end{cases}$ $\mu_1 = \begin{cases} 2a, & \xi \leq 0, \\ 2a - \xi, & \xi > 0. \end{cases}$

The internal integral in (11) is calculated analytically, while the external integral is calculated numerically. It should be noted that the integrand has a logarithmic singularity at $\xi = 0$. To eliminate it, the integration interval should be divided so that the singularity falls on one of the boundary points of the partial integration intervals, and the Gaussian quadrature formula can be used to calculate the partial integrals. In addition, due to the property of relation (6), which consists in the fact that $\sigma_{ms} = \sigma_{sm}$, the calculation of the half of the specified number of coefficients may not be performed.

The right side of SLAE (8) is determined by the value of the coefficients J_{si} and P_{si} . The calculation of the coefficients P_{si} in accordance with the relation (7) takes most of the time. However, the uniformity of the expressions (6) and (7) indicates the possibility of modifying (7). Indeed, by using the properties of the Fourier transform, one can obtain a more suitable expression for the numerical calculation of the coefficients P_{si} :

$$P_{si} = \frac{1}{2} \int_{x_{li}-2a}^{x_{li}} H_0^{(1)}(k|\xi + a|) \int_{v_l}^{v_1} \cos\left(\frac{s\pi\mu}{2a}\right) \exp[j\beta_i(\mu + \xi)] d\mu d\xi,$$

where $v_l = \begin{cases} x_{li} - \xi, & \xi \leq x_{li}, \\ 0, & \xi > x_{li}; \end{cases}$ $v_1 = \begin{cases} 2a, & \xi \leq x_{li} - 2a, \\ x_{li} - \xi, & \xi > x_{li} - 2a. \end{cases}$

If the area of a direct interaction of an electromagnetic wave with a groove has a large extension, that is $2\Delta l_i = x_{li} - x_{li} \gg \lambda$, then, to ensure a high accuracy in calculating the coefficients P_{si} , it makes sense to divide the fragment of the exposure band $2\Delta l_i$ into the parts $[x_{lij}, x_{lij}]$ with the reference to the groove. So, it is reasonable to single out the interval $[-2a, 2a]$ corresponding to the area of a direct exposure of the groove, as well as the parts to the left and to the right of the groove with a length of no more than $\lambda/2$. If the j -th part of the exposed band fragment is significantly far from the groove, for example $x_{lij} \geq a + (1\dots 2)\lambda$, then the calculation of the j -th integral as part of P_{si} can be performed using an approximate formula. Such a formula can be obtained from the original one by the change of the Hankel function by its asymptotic approximation with a subsequent analytical integration involving quiescing the argument of the root of the integrand denominator [28]:

$$P_{sj} \approx \frac{k \exp[-j(\pi/4 - ka/2)] [1 - (-1)^s \exp(-jka)] [\exp(jx_{lij}(\beta_i + k)) - \exp(jx_{lij}(\beta_i - k))]}{\sqrt{\pi k (x_{lij} + x_{lij})} [k^2 - (s\pi/a)^2] (\beta_i + k)}. \quad (12)$$

If $x_{lij} \leq -a/2 - (1\dots 2)\lambda$, the wave number sign k should be reversed in (12).

Thus, the generated mathematical model of the diffraction of an electromagnetic wave with a complex amplitude-phase front on a rectangular groove in a conducting screen compares favourably with the traditional model. The traditional approach uses the Fourier expansion of a wave beam in terms of the flat waves unbounded in space [18]-[21], which implies a multiple solution of the problem of diffraction of a flat wave arriving at different angles on a screen with a groove. The need for multiple solutions to the traditional SLAE leads to significant computational costs. In the generated model, the number of divisions of the amplitude-phase front of the beam of electromagnetic waves in the plane of the screen into the locally flat patches affects only the number of terms on the

right side of the SLAE (8), and, as a result, the computation time required to solve the problem is affected insignificantly. At the same time, the coefficients of the main matrix of SLAE (8) do not depend on the quality of the interpolation of the field exciting the groove by locally flat waves and are calculated only once. The produced SLAE is also solved once, which ultimately guarantees a reduction in computational costs compared to the traditional approach. The gain increases remarkably, if there are tens or hundreds of grooves in the screen, which is typical for the comb-type distribution and radiating systems of the certain classes of modern antennas [7]-[17].

In Fig. 3 one can see the normalized amplitude scattering diagrams obtained based on the presented digital model that demonstrate the scattering of a two-dimensional Gaussian wave beam with an effective size 1.5λ , which arrives at the angle $\varphi=0^\circ$ (along the normal) and exposes a band of the length $2\Delta=10\lambda$ that the groove in the screen produces.

FIGURE 3. The scattering diagrams demonstrating the scattering of the Gaussian beam by the groove with the depth $\lambda/4$ and the width: 1 – 1.5λ ; 2 – 3λ ; 3– 5λ .

When calculating the first term in the expression (9), as well as the factor $\cos\Theta$ in the formula (10) are omitted. The number of points of division of the wave beam front has been taken in the course of calculations with a deliberate excess and it is equal to 1000. The groove has the depth $h = \lambda/4$, and the groove width $2a$ is from 1.5λ to 5λ . The corresponding scattering diagrams obtained using the traditional approach are given in [29]. The superimposition of the scattering diagrams obtained while using the developed model with the scattering diagrams presented in [29] indicates their coincidence within the limits of a graphical accuracy. The dotted lines in Fig. 3 shows scattering diagrams produced by a groove of a flat plane wave with an exposure band having the length of 10λ . Since the band exposed by a locally flat wave on the screen surface significantly exceeds the width of the groove, this mode is equivalent to the case of the excitation due to the flat wave with a spatially unbounded front. The comparison with scattering diagrams similar in meaning in [29] indicates their identity.

THE MATHEMATICAL MODEL TESTING

After the verification of the generated computational algorithm, it seems appropriate to estimate the influence of the quality of the interpolation of the front of the primary wave interacting with the groove in the screen on the error in calculating the groove response. As the latter, one should consider not the amplitude scattering diagram, since it is weakly sensitive to the higher waveguide modes excited in the groove and significantly affecting the diffraction field in the near zone, but the amplitudes and initial phases of the waveguide modes [30].

Now, one chooses the E -sectoral optimal horn to be used as the source of the electromagnetic field, placed above the screen at the height $z_0 = 25\lambda$ and exposing the groove along the normal to the plane of its aperture. It is assumed that the maximum of the horn directional pattern falls on the center of the groove ($x_0 = 0$), and the characteristic size of the horn aperture is chosen so that the main lobe of the primary amplitude field distribution on the screen surface has the length of 2λ . The width of the groove $2a$ is taken equal to λ , while its depth is $h = \lambda/4$. The length of the groove exposure band, taking into account the presence of the side lobes of the amplitude distribution, is $2\Delta = 10\lambda$. To estimate the convergence, the solution of the problem obtained by dividing the wave front into 1000 fragments ($K = 1000$) is used as an exact one. It should be noted that the formulated particular problem of diffraction is not trivial. To solve it, the computational algorithm presented above is used.

In Table 1, for the different values of the number of discretization points of the primary wave front (K), one can see the relative (in percent) errors in calculating the amplitudes of the waveguide modes of the groove in the screen that are of 0-, 2-, and 4-th orders ($\delta D_0, \delta D_2, \delta D_4$), as well as the absolute (in degrees) residuals of their initial phases ($\Delta \psi_0, \Delta \psi_2, \Delta \psi_4$).

TABLE 1. The convergence of the solution of a particular problem of diffraction on a groove in the screen with an increase in the accuracy of interpolation of the front of the primary wave by the locally flat waves.

K	5	10	15	20	25	30	40	50	75	100
$\delta D_0, \%$	12.25	-28.66	-7.00	-0.18	-1.72	-2.12	0.12	-0.78	-0.26	< 0.01
$\Delta \psi_0, ^\circ$	-0.62	2.94	0.51	-0.89	0.06	0.18	-0.06	0.03	< 0.01	< 0.01
$\delta D_2, \%$	83.34	19.67	35.25	-0.90	-2.53	-2.65	1.67	-1.28	-0.39	0.31
$\Delta \psi_2, ^\circ$	-19.31	-13.66	36.29	-15.75	-2.40	2.78	-3.41	0.87	0.04	-0.44
$\delta D_4, \%$	95.59	22.81	-35.35	10.19	87.95	-49.15	29.81	-9.14	-0.97	3.16
$\Delta \psi_4, ^\circ$	17.33	22.26	-121.3	20.89	8.49	-26.78	9.55	-4.21	-0.56	1.77

It follows from Table 1 that the relative and absolute residuals decrease with an increasing K . The nature of the residual value attenuation is oscillatory. At $K = 100$, the amplitude calculation error magnitude, including the 4-th mode, is reduced to 3%, while the magnitudes of the initial phase residuals are reduced to 1.8° . The specified accuracy of the solution, as numerical estimates show, is quite sufficient for a reliable calculation of the diffraction field intensities in the near zone of the groove.

So, when discretizing the wave front into 100 points, i.e. when it is divided in the plane of the screen into flat fragments of the length 0.1λ , within the main lobe of the primary amplitude distribution 20 such fragments fit on the screen with the groove, and 10 such fragments – within the radiating groove aperture. When solving the problem of the electromagnetic wave beam diffraction on a groove in the screen and accounting for the near field calculation, one should be guided by the above estimates. If the primary amplitude distribution of the beam in the screen plane is two times or wider than the groove, then at least 10 nodes of the wave front interpolation should be marked in the groove aperture. If the characteristic size of the amplitude distribution corresponds to or is less than twice the width of the groove, then the number of nodes is 20 or more in terms of the distribution width. If it is necessary to calculate the field in the far zone, the recommended values can be safely halved.

CONCLUSION

In this paper, a numerical mathematical model is produced for the scattering of a linear H -polarization electromagnetic wave with a complex amplitude-phase front on a rectangular groove in a conducting unbounded screen. The primary wave front interpolation in the plane of the screen by an aggregate of the locally flat fragments is used. The problem is reduced to a finite SLAE, the main matrix of which is identical to the SLAE matrix characteristic of the problem of diffraction on a groove in the screen of a locally flat wave with a bounded front. The presented solution to the diffraction problem can be considered rigorous, like the solution in [29], since it uses only a computational approximation and, like any rigorous solution, can be applied in a wide range of changes in the characteristics of the primary wave and the diffraction system. The computational algorithm is verified and its adequacy and reliability are demonstrated. The convergence of the solution of a nontrivial problem of diffraction on a groove in the screen is studied with an increase in the accuracy of interpolation of the primary wave front by the locally flat waves. The recommendations are formulated for choosing the number of discretization points for the primary wave amplitude-phase front for a reliable calculation of the diffraction field in the near and far zones. The presented computational algorithm can be used to analyze the properties of the finite combs of a rectangular profile when excited by a concentrated source of an electromagnetic field. Based on this analysis, this algorithm can be applied to synthesize antennas incorporating the flat comb-type distribution and radiating systems, characterized by the different methods of excitation.

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